

THE SIGNIFICANCE OF LASER LEVELING OF IRRIGATED AREAS TODAY

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Abstract: In this article, we will mainly write about the importance of leveling irrigated fields with a laser leveler today, as well as the advantages and disadvantages of the laser leveler.

Key words: laser leveler, land, irrigation, agrotechnics, agriculture.

Leveling of irrigated fields is among all agrotechnical tools for improving the melioration of irrigated fields and obtaining high yields from crops. The main reason for this is that when properly leveled, the water given for irrigation or for saline loading is distributed uniformly throughout the irrigated area, and also adjusts the agrotechnical additives. If the irrigated areas are not properly leveled, the level of water for irrigation or saline loading will increase, and then the land reclamation condition will deteriorate, saline patches will appear. Flattening the land helps to move forward with higher productivity from irrigation water, fertilizers and mechanized production. Leveled fields provide good conditions for plant growth and development. In fields that are not well leveled, the planted plants will not be clearly produced, the uniform germination of seedlings will improve, the quality of irrigation and subsequent inter-row feeding will deteriorate, and the application of fertilizer will be strengthened. Rainfall and irrigation water are unevenly distributed

in such fields. There is not enough moisture for the crops in the fallow areas, it is difficult to get water to such lands, and the water that comes out is good for the soil and drains quickly. In the lowlands, the water accumulates and the humidity increases, and the plants rot. The microrelief frost and the different soil water regime in the lowlands lead to its simultaneous ripening. When following the row distance, the soil is not worked evenly, at some level it is not softened, and at another level it becomes flaky and pus, as a result of which the plowed land has a strong soil moisture, as a result, the moisture loss increases. . Fertilizer is distributed to the field with water. When the ground is uneven, nutrients are distributed unevenly to the field, which further increases the uneven development of the plant. There is a special enterprise in the fight against soil salinity, leveling works on lands with poor melioration status. In unlevelled, saline soils, the grain of the seedling is uneven. Up to 30% of the planted area can be vegetated. There is a lot of large salt in the soil of the places where the plant does not grow. During salt washing and irrigation, such areas are not wetted enough and, therefore, not enough salt is washed away.

If we talk about leveling the land on a laser leveler, then the difference between the lowest and highest places in the power of the field does not exceed 1-3 cm. Laser land leveling involves the main tractor, tractor, leveling equipment and laser device. The operation of the laser device is based on the following: laser transmitter (transmitter), light receiver (receiver), data control (block) device, electrohydraulic valve (solenoid hydrovalve).

As we all know that everything has advantages and disadvantages, there are advantages and disadvantages of leveling irrigated areas with a laser leveler, for example, we can cite the following:

Advantages of leveling on a laser leveler:

- Irrigation water consumption is saved by 20-25%;
- Water use efficiency increases by 30-40%;
- Excess salt is prevented from coming through irrigation water;

- The reclamation condition of irrigated areas will improve;
- Watering time, manpower and energy are saved;
- Crops in the field have uniform fertility;
- Crops are provided with the same nutrients and moisture;
- The amount of weeds is reduced;
- If the tillage is carried out correctly, the field area will be leveled again in 3-

5 years.

- Leveling of irrigated lands is more accurate than traditional leveling.

Disadvantages of leveling on a laser leveler:

- Technical parts of the laser leveler are economically expensive;
- Costs are high compared to traditional leveling;
- There is a high probability of being damaged due to lack of user training;
- Compacts the land compared to traditional leveling;
- If the plowing works are carried out well, it will be necessary to level every

year.

Today, a number of land leveling devices have been created in the world. Ground leveling devices differ from each other in terms of technology, performance, leveling ability and other indicators, but today laser leveling devices stand out from other leveling devices.

In conclusion, it can be said that by introducing modern technologies in agriculture, we can increase the productivity of agricultural crops, save water resources, improve the melioration of irrigated areas, prevent irrigation erosion, and achieve a number of other achievements.

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